

NUTRACEUTICAL PROSPECTS OF BROWN RICE VARIETIES COLLECTED FROM PAKISTAN: A RESERVOIR OF NUTRIENTS AND PHYTOCHEMICALS

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ABSTRACT

Rice (Oryza sativa) is regarded as one of the most essential food crops and is widely consumed around the world. Pakistan is a key rice-producing country that not only supplies enough to meet local needs but also exports significant quantities. The primary objective of this review was to investigate the nutraceutical potential of brown rice varieties and their associated health benefits, with a special focus on Pakistani varieties. In Pakistan, most people rely on rice to meet their basic dietary needs. Several studies have indicated that brown rice offers nutrigenomic benefits, including anti-diabetic, anti-cholesterol, cardio-protective, and antioxidant effects, due to the phytochemicals concentrated in the bran layer. Recent evidence supports that consuming brown rice varieties is advantageous for health. Brown rice contains an array of bioactive compounds, including phenolics, flavonoids, anthocyanins, proanthocyanidins, tocopherols, tocotrienols, phytic acid, dietary fiber, lipids, and essential amino acids, all of which play important roles in metabolic processes and help defend against various diseases. Therefore, future research should focus on analyzing the bioactive compounds in rice varieties cultivated in Balochistan and their potential health impacts.

Introduction to Brown Rice Varieties

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is one of the most widely consumed staple foods worldwide, and its nutritional quality varies depending on the degree of milling. Brown rice, produced by removing only the outer husk and retaining the bran and germ layers, is increasingly recognized as a functional food due to its dense concentration of bioactive compounds (Goufo & Trindade, 2014). Unlike polished white rice, brown rice contains substantial amounts of dietary fibre, vitamins, minerals, and phytochemicals such as phenolic acids, flavonoids, γ -oryzanol, and tocopherols, which contribute to its antioxidant, cholesterol-lowering, and anti-diabetic properties (Iqbal, Bhangar, & Anwar, 2011; Tan, Norhaizan, & Chan, 2023). It is believed that rice was the first crop cultivated in Asia. The preserved rice grains were discovered in China, dating back to 3000 BC (Fuller et al., 2010). Rice is extensively cultivated throughout Pakistan, particularly in the Punjab region. Pakistan ranks fourth globally in rice exports and eleventh among the world's largest rice-producing countries. It is the largest producer of both Basmati and non-Basmati rice, especially Basmati super. Punjab and Sindh are the two main provinces, with six regions producing Basmati rice, including varieties such as Super Basmati, Basmati 385, Basmati 198, Basmati Pak, and Basmati 515. In Pakistan, Basmati and IRRI cultivars are widely grown, with brown forms of Basmati varieties demonstrating particularly high nutraceutical potential (Zubair, Anwar, & Shahid, 2012). However, the consumption of brown rice remains limited in South Asia, mainly due to sensory preferences, cooking qualities, and storage challenges. As research into nutraceuticals progresses, the significance of brown rice as a sustainable functional food and source of bioactive compounds deserves more recognition.

Nutritional Prospects of Brown Rice

Rice is dominant among cereal grains due to its important quality-oriented characteristics, including carbohydrates, crude protein, crude fiber, crude fat, moisture, vitamins, and ash content, which enable it to be differentiated from other cereal grains (Yu, J., *et al.*, 2022). Rice comprises about 75-85% carbohydrates. Carbohydrate is the primary source of energy that is utilized by human in their daily life. Carbohydrate is generally found in the form of starch in both brown and white rice. The ten selected Pakistani rice varieties were assessed for carbohydrate content and ranged between 0.173-0.186 g/100g (Zubair, Anwar, & Shahid, 2012). Starch is present in high concentration in the inner endosperm of rice (Zhou, Robards, Helliwell, & Blanchard, 2002). The starch is a major source of carbohydrates in rice and a

polymer that comprises two glucans (amylose and amylopectin). The rice is also composed of reduced sugar, glutelin, albumen, globulin, and prolamine (Burlando & Cornara, 2014). After starch, the protein is the second important constituent of rice. There are four types of protein fractions commonly present in both brown and white rice, which include albumin, globulin, glutelin, and prolamin. Albumin is water-soluble, globulin is salt-soluble, glutelin is alkali-soluble, while prolamin is alcohol-soluble (Amagliani *et al.*, 2017). Several studies have quantified the protein and amino acid concentrations of brown rice, with protein content ranging from 5.4% to 11.9%. The protein concentration of brown rice varies depending upon geographical region and genetic variation (Bryant *et al.*, 2013). In a study conducted by Asmaa & Afifa (2021),

The concentration of protein in Pakistani organic brown rice variety was 9.20%. The protein is primarily found in the bran part of rice and is lost during the milling process. Rice is a hypoallergenic food crop, and the protein digestibility and biological value are greater compared to other cereal crops. Rice protein is considered beneficial due to its balanced amino acid composition and various applications, including use as a functional food ingredient in infant formula and sports nutrition (Amagliani *et al.*, 2017). Among the 10 Pakistani rice varieties, seven types of amino acids were identified, including arginine, glutamic acid, leucine, isoleucine, phenylalanine, methionine, and tyrosine. The glutamic amino acid, which is acidic in nature, had a higher concentration of approximately 1.51g/100g in Basmati Super (Zubair, Anwar, & Shahid, 2012). In a study, 16 amino acids were reported to be present in both brown and white rice, with eight of these being essential, except for tryptophan. The amino acid lysine is rich in the protein (Thomas, Bhat, & Kaung, 2015). Therefore, interchanging white rice with brown rice in the human diet is expected to provide more protein and amino acids, which is good for health and well-being (Kalman, 2014). Brown, rough-milled rice comprises nearly 8% and 7% protein (Araullo *et al.*, 1976). In the Asian diet, rice makes up roughly 28-54% of the total protein, 20% of all nutritious protein, and 27% of all nutritional energy in the world. Its digestibility, biological worth, and protein efficiency ratio are all comparatively higher than other cereal crops (Bashir *et al.*, 2007).

Brown rice is also composed of high levels of dietary fiber, which has been considered to prevent colorectal cancer and breast cancer (Aune *et al.*, 2011). In an animal study, rice bran from brown rice was shown to be beneficial in preventing the development of polyps in the bowel (Verschoyle *et al.*, 2007). The fiber concentrated in the foods increases the digestive system and is associated with a decrease in the risk of intestinal diseases (Sotelo *et al.*, 1990). In different Pakistani rice varieties, fiber content ranged between 0.20 to 0.35%.

The milled brown rice provides 1.9% fiber (Tufail, 1997). In another Pakistani rice variety organic brown rice the fiber content was 1.29% (Asmaa % Afifa, 2021). It is observed that half cup of cooked brown rice provides 1.8 g of dietary fiber, which is higher when compared to white rice. Rice bran is a key source of both soluble and insoluble dietary fibre, with a significant contribution of 20 to 51%, which is twice that of oat bran. In contrast to white rice, brown rice contains a low glycemic index (Foster-Powell *et al.*, 2002). Consuming more brown rice compared to white rice results in improved endothelial function (Kondo *et al.*, 2017).

Lipid is considered the third most significant component of brown rice after carbohydrate and protein. Fat is found in the germ layer and bran part of rice, accounting for about 20% of total mass. The lipid concentration is comparatively higher in brown rice than in white rice (milled rice). Lipids play a key role in the quality of rice during processing and storage (Thomas *et al.*, 2015; Zhou *et al.*, 2002). Unsaturated fatty acids are abundantly present in brown rice, including oleic and linoleic acids. In a study, the composition of fatty acids in 120 Korean native cultivars of brown rice was found to be 21.2% palmitic acid, 1.8% stearic acid, 36.5% oleic acid, and 36.3% linoleic acid. Therefore, consuming brown rice provides a good source of healthy fatty acids for those incorporating rice into their daily diet (Cho, Kim, Lee, Kang, & Lee, 2006). Along with other nutritional parameters, the moisture content of rice grains is a very important characteristic, as whole grains are stored for a specific period before consumption. A higher moisture content makes rice more challenging to store properly because it increases susceptibility to diseases, pest attacks, and hydrolytic changes (Gooding & Davies, 1997). In a study conducted by Stanley (1986) and Awan (1996), rice varieties showed a moisture content range of 7 to 11%. Moisture content in rice grains is typically measured using the oven drying method, as documented by Dowell *et al.*, (2002). Simultaneously, ash content is a crucial factor in evaluating flour quality. A range of ash content between 0.57% and 0.82% was observed in some rice varieties, as explored by Awan (1996), whereas Sotelo *et al.*, (1990) reported a range from 1.4% to 1.9% in brown rice varieties.

Bioactive Phytochemicals and Antioxidant Activity in Brown Rice

The bioactive phytochemical composition of brown rice includes phenolics, flavonoids, anthocyanins, proanthocyanidins, tocopherols, tocotrienols, phytic acid, γ -oryzanol, mineral nutrients, and (GABA) gamma-aminobutyric acid (Wu *et al.*, 2013; Umadevi *et al.*, 2012). These compounds contribute to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, cholesterol-lowering, and anti-diabetic potential compared with polished white rice (Iqbal, Bhangar, & Anwar, 2011).

Among all parameters, the phenolics are categorized under the classification of phytochemicals, which have one or more aromatic rings along with one or more hydroxyl groups. These components play a crucial role in human health, exhibiting anti-inflammatory, hypoglycemic, anti-carcinogenic, anti-allergenic, and anti-atherosclerotic properties (Tan *et al.*, 2017). The types of phenolic compounds are phenolic acid, flavonoids, tannins, coumarins, and stilbenes (Liu *et al.*, 2007). Brown rice is considered an amazing source of these phenolics (Gong *et al.*, 2017). The phenolics are present in rice in three different forms: free phenolic, soluble conjugated, and bound forms. The major form of phenolic is the bound form. The bran and germ part of rice is rich in these compounds (Adom *et al.*, 2005). When brown rice is milled, it results in the loss of these components, and they cannot be easily preserved. The primary phenolic compounds present in brown rice are p-hydroxybenzoic acid and p-hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives (Liu *et al.*, 2007).

Another main type of phenolic acid is *trans-p-coumaric* acid, found in brown rice. The *cis*-ferulic acid is also a type of phenolic acid that is widely distributed in bound form in brown rice (Gong *et al.*, 2017). The free phenolics help in absorption present in the small intestine, whereas bound phenolics are preserved throughout the intestinal tract and released in the bowel, where they communicate with micro microbiome to favor the Bacteroides ratio (Martinez *et al.*, 2013). Hepatic fibrosis, a disease, can be prevented by consuming brown rice varieties.

Soluble phenolic compounds are made up of free phenolic acids and hydroxycinnamate sucrose esters (Tian *et al.*, 2004). The feruloyl sucrose, sinapoyl sucrose, and ferulic acid are the major soluble phenolic compounds found in brown rice. These are readily available components in brown rice that are in bound form, like 8-O-4 diferulic acid, ranging from (13.88-22.61 $\mu\text{g/g}$), 8-5' benzofuran DFA ranged between (9.28-14.79 $\mu\text{g/g}$). The other three derivatives of hydroxycinnamic acid are caffeic acid, sinapic acid, and chlorogenic acid, which ranged between 0.00-1.44 $\mu\text{g/g}$, 1.19-1.25 $\mu\text{g/g}$, and 0.63 $\mu\text{g/g}$, respectively (Gong *et al.*, 2017). Unlike white rice, brown rice is rich in diverse phytochemical compounds and antioxidants (Caceres *et al.*, 2017). However, due to the presence of high-nutritional-value compounds, brown rice is less consumed compared to white rice because of its extended cooking time, higher cost, and limited availability (Adebamowo *et al.*, 2017). The phenolic compounds are responsible for antioxidant activity by protecting cells against oxidative damage, thereby reducing the risk of diseases related to oxidative stress. These compounds also protect against diseases like type 2 diabetes, obesity, and cancer, which is possible due to the high antioxidant levels present in brown rice (Shao *et al.*, 2015).

Among phytochemicals, the flavonoids were also detected in brown rice, which has antioxidant potential. The chemical structure of flavonoids is composed of a 15-carbon skeleton, which is further comprised of two aromatic rings associated with a heterocyclic ring. The flavonoids owe their antioxidant activity to their phenolic groups. The common type of flavonoids which is found in brown rice is flavones, and tricetin is the main type of flavonoid, which contributes to 75% of the total flavonoids in brown rice. Other types of flavonoids, like luteolin, apigenin, quercetin, isorhamnetin, kaempferol, and myricetin, are present in low amounts (Goufo & Trindade, 2014).

Anthocyanins are another important phenolic component in sub subclass of flavonoids found in brown rice. These compounds exist as polyhydroxylated and methoxylated heterosides and are derivatives of the flavylum ion or 2-phenylbenzopyrylium. In pigmented rice, anthocyanins appear in various forms, including cyanidin 3-glucoside, cyanidin di-glucoside, and cyanidin 3-galactoside, among others (Chen *et al.*, 2013).

Through their reactive oxygen species (ROS) scavenging activity, these phytochemicals play a crucial role in actively defending cells against oxidative damage. Historically, rice has been used for medicinal purposes, especially within Ayurveda, which has extensively utilized the crop. Common applications include vitamin supplementation, skin care, and treatment of gastrointestinal disorders, diarrhoea, and anti-inflammatory uses for conditions like diabetes (Goufo & Trindade, 2014). Pro-anthocyanidins (PA) are high-molecular-weight polymers, known as condensed tannins, present in cereals and legumes. These complex flavonoid polymers are composed of flavan-3-ol units, such as (+)- catechin and (-)- epicatechin. The presence of these polymeric compounds is responsible for the reddish color of the testa (Chen *et al.*, 2016). They also play a vital role in plant defense against both biotic and abiotic stresses (Zhao & Dixon, 2010).

Other bioactive phytochemicals, such as various forms of Vitamin E, were also studied in different types of brown rice. Among these, the most commonly detected were two main groups: tocopherols (α , β , and δ forms) and tocotrienols (α , β , γ , and δ forms) (Okarter *et al.*, 2010). A wide range of traditional rice varieties with genetic diversity show significant properties, including medicinal and aromatic potentials. Local rice varieties are considered excellent sources of bioactive non-nutrient compounds. Additionally, these rice cultivars are rich in nutritional bioactive compounds like riboflavin, vitamin D, niacin, thiamine (vitamin B1), and vitamin B2 (riboflavin) (Varma *et al.*, 2018). Vitamin E functions as an antioxidant, maintains membrane integrity, participates in DNA repair mechanisms, supports the immune system, and plays a role in metabolic processes (Liu *et al.*, 2007). The

sterols were also found in brown rice. The most common sterol is γ -oryzanol, which is found in rich amounts in brown rice, a ferulic acid ester of major phytosterols. The ten Pakistani rice varieties revealed the presence of γ -oryzanol components, which were further composed of four components, including gamma-oryzanol, 24-methylene cycloartanyl ferulate, campesteryl ferulate and β -sitosteryl ferulate. Overall, the concentration of these components was high in Basmati varieties (Basmati Super, Basmati Pak, and Basmati 370), indicating a high antioxidant nutritional potency in these rice varieties (Zubair, Anwar, & Shahid, 2012). The γ -oryzanol performs several physiological functions, including effects on anthropometry, muscle function, cholesterol lowering, and anti-cancer characteristics. The γ -oryzanol also exhibits pharmacological functions, including anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, and antioxidant activities (Panlasigui & Thompson, 2006).

Studies on Pakistani germplasm have shown that Basmati cultivars, such as Basmati 2000, Basmati 515, and Basmati Pak, have significantly higher total phenolic content (TPC) and antioxidant activity in their brown rice forms (Zubair, Anwar, & Shahid, 2012). Solvent systems, particularly aqueous methanol and isopropanol, enhance the recovery of these antioxidants, highlighting methodological considerations for accurate nutraceutical assessment (Zubair *et al.*, 2012).

Pigmented Brown Rice and Unique Compounds

Pigmented brown rice (red, purple, and black varieties) contains anthocyanins and proanthocyanidins, which are associated with potent radical scavenging activities and protective effects against cardiovascular and metabolic diseases (Goufo & Trindade, 2014). Although pigmented landraces are less widely grown in Pakistan, they represent an underexplored genetic resource for diversifying nutraceutical-rich rice varieties.

Functional Health Benefits

Nutraceuticals are functional foods that offer health advantages beyond disease prevention and protection. Similarly, products with therapeutic qualities focus on the development of remedial agents and treatments for diseases. For instance, rice bran or rice constituents possess several pharmacological properties that make them potential components for a therapeutic nutraceutical, including immunomodulatory, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticancer, cardiovascular protective, anti-hyperlipidemic, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, and antimicrobial properties (Sen *et al.*, 2020). Clinical and nutritional evidence suggest that consuming brown rice improves glycemic response, making it a suitable option for individuals with diabetes (Umnajkitikorn, Ferreira, & Pintado, 2013). Its high dietary fiber content further contributes to satiety, gut health, and lipid regulation. This positions brown rice as a potential dietary intervention in South Asian populations where

diabetes and obesity are increasing. In the present era, nutritionists are recommending that patients consume brown rice-based foods. Various clinical reports are demonstrating that consumption of Brown rice is associated with reducing the risk of particular chronic illnesses like, cardiovascular disorders, type-2 diabetes, obesity, and different kinds of cancers (Sun *et al.*, 2010). Several studies have suggested that Brown rice exhibits anti-diabetic properties compared to white rice and has the potential to lower the starch digestion rate and glycemic response (Shobana *et al.*, 2017).

Challenges and Processing Considerations

Despite its nutritional superiority, the adoption of brown rice in Pakistan is limited due to its chewy texture, extended cooking time, and shorter shelf-life caused by lipid rancidity in the bran (Tan *et al.*, 2023). Latest technologies, such as the milling process of rice, which produces white rice, is another key factor regarding less consumption of brown rice (Selvam, Masilamani, Umashankar, & Albert, 2017). The shelf life is another factor that limits the consumption of Brown rice; however, various techniques are being invented to enhance its shelf life. Techniques such as parboiling, bran stabilization, and modified storage conditions are necessary to improve consumer acceptance and marketability.

Future Prospects in Pakistan

Brown rice varieties, particularly Basmati and pigmented types, are a valuable but underutilized source of nutraceutical compounds. Enhancing research on their bioactive potential, promoting the cultivation of pigmented landraces, and developing bran stabilization technologies can significantly increase their role in the development of functional foods and nutraceutical markets in Pakistan.

Conclusion

Brown rice is a rich source of nutritional and phytochemical bioactive compounds, which are associated with several important health benefits compared to white rice. The screening of the nutraceutical composition of rice varieties consumed in daily life is crucial for humans, as it fulfils basic needs and mitigates health-related problems. Therefore, understanding and exploring the nutraceutical potential of rice is essential for evaluating its nutrigenomic implications in human health. The rice contains various bioactive components like crude protein, crude fiber, crude fat, carbohydrates, phenolics, flavonoids, anthocyanin, proanthocyanidin, tocopherols, tocotrienols, phytic acid, dietary fiber, lipids, and essential amino acids, which play a crucial role in metabolic processes and help to protect from various diseases. In the current era of food insecurity, knowledge of the nutraceutical composition of different rice varieties may further increase awareness among farmers to cultivate more of

these varieties with superior nutraceutical properties, enabling food producers to market them effectively. Although the nutraceutical properties of rice in Balochistan are rarely studied, considerable attention is currently needed for evaluating the valuable components found in rice varieties grown in Balochistan. Therefore, it is recommended that all commonly consumed rice varieties be evaluated for their nutraceutical potential.

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